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Assessing an ‘incentives-driven’ approach to engage undergraduate engineering students in a developing Pacific country

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ABSTRACT

The unexpected and non-linear growth of IT products has challenged the way in which students have traditionally been taught in classrooms. Innovation in teaching has been the focus for many teachers who want to keep up with burgeoning IT tools and make their classes interesting. This study focuses on using an incentive-driven approach supported by technology-based teaching methods, used in one undergraduate engineering course at a university in a developing country in the Pacific region. Students in the course are not only from different Pacific island countries namely Fiji, Solomon Islands, Vanuatu, Tuvalu, Kiribati, and Tonga where they had little or no exposure to technology support but come from diverse ethnic and cultural backgrounds. Data from students were collected using online forms and analyzed qualitatively. The findings suggest that students learned better and enhanced their skills when innovative methods like group learning, Facebook groups, Peer assessments and team work were introduced. Students are motivated to learn and participate in classroom activities when incentives encourage their achievements. Students' wish for similar teaching methods to be used in other courses highlights the need for engineering teachers in any context to focus on innovation and incentives in classrooms and for policy makers in universities to encourage such approaches in order to provide a more relevant and effective learning platform for students.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Engineering skills, Attractiveness of Engineering Education.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This paper describes and assesses the effect of an incentive-driven approach, based on various innovative strategies, in a computing science engineering course for a period of 13 weeks during semester 1, 2015 at The University of the South Pacific. Hence, we set ourselves the following research question: How do incentive-based innovative strategies used in engineering class impact these students?

The objective was to see if students in a new developing country context would find them useful and whether it would encourage engaged learning. Given the continuing advances in Information Technology (IT) and IT tools, teaching and learning methods need to change rapidly. The students are way ahead, with numerous gadgets readily available at their disposal. Based on our experience teaching undergraduate courses in Australia and India, we found computing students hard to motivate to attend lectures or other learning activities. Many participate in lectures or assessments only for attendance marks or if the lecture covers exam topics. They miss important concepts if they don't attend lectures or tutorials but if classes are not interesting there is little motivation to attend. The experience of using innovative methods with Australian and Indian computing students sparked this study to ascertain if they were also suitable in a diverse Pacific island context.

The University of the South Pacific, in Suva, serves students from eleven different Pacific countries and some remote Pacific islands. Fiji has around 900,000 people in 2017 and is multi-racial and multi-cultural. Indigenous Fijians are the main ethnic group (54%) with Indo-Fijians around 40% and declining. The indigenous Fijians are mainly Protestant Christians; the Indo-Fijians are mainly Hindu, with small Muslim and Sikh communities. For various reasons, there is tension between the ethnic groups. This makes effective teaching, particularly in terms of inclusive teamwork, even more important. Moreover, a modern lifestyle and infrastructure pose challenges to students before they even start classes. Internet coverage is good in Fiji, but unstable in other Pacific countries. This study was based on student group that includes indigenous Fijians, Indian Fijians and students from other Pacific nations such as Kiribati, Tuvalu, Solomon Islands and Vanuatu. They are aged between 18 and 35. The average age of the participants was 22 and 30% of the respondents were female. The data were collected in the form of anonymous online survey towards the end of the teaching period and results were analyzed qualitatively.

Two terms are commonly used within this paper: approaches and methods. Approaches refer to general philosophies used in teaching while methods refer to the practical aspects of teaching. The findings indicate that these students benefited from the incentive-based approach using innovative teaching methods and IT tools and moreover, that they would welcome such strategies in other courses. The benefits include learning creative skills, benefiting from group learning, motivation to learn new skills and learning to work as team players. It justifies continuing to invest in and encourage teaching innovations in a developing nation context where there are so many other demands on funding.

In the following sections we review innovative approaches. We then describe the methodology, before outlining the findings, limitations and conclusion.

2 INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

The traditional (and still common) approach used a quiz, assignments and a final exam, which have the obvious advantages of being easier to administer and mark. The contrasts between the enriched innovative approach and the traditional approach are illustrated in Figure 1 below. The exponential growth in IT has created jobs that were not part of organizational structures a few decades ago [1, 2]. This has created new challenges for teachers, including how to establish the conditions to help students learn [3]. Researchers are now focusing on specific technological tools [4-6] such as how a participative learning setup, assisted by ICT, would help teachers to keep the learners interested and motivated [7]. Every few years a new disruptive technology emerges, i.e. something that fundamentally changes the way we do things [8]. For example, the Internet, mobile devices and Virtual Learning Environments, Smartphones, mobile devices and tablets have advantaged students who use them, for instance in catching up with any missed lectures [9]. They provide complementary support for students working in a second or other language, as it gives them more opportunities to listen and take meaningful notes or reflect on content. Tapp [10] found that podcasting helped students in this way. Teachers can improve student interest by introducing tasks that are imaginative and involve reflective thinking, fostering creativity and out-of-the-box thinking ideas.

Fig. 1. Teaching model deployed in CS240

Innovative approaches [11] include the use of multimedia, a combination of different digital media [12], interactive applications and presentation tools. Humor has proven effective, as it creates a conducive environment for learning and communication [13]. A study by Missildine et al. [14] to test the effectiveness of a flipped class room approach – a pedagogical model where typical lectures and home work in a course are reversed, indicates that students managed to score higher examination grades. Student satisfaction was also higher than in traditional lecture-only approaches. Robson and et al [15] report that a case study approach to teaching innovation encourages students to participate actively in learning. Scenarios have been effective, especially for students from science and engineering disciplines, as they foster decision making [13]. Wilson's study on the implications of using evidence-based assignments in an undergraduate course indicates that students

tend to gain more knowledge and are better prepared to identify problems in practice and understand them better in order to conduct systematic reviews [16].

Many studies reveal that higher education should focus on meeting the individual needs of learners [17, 18]. Innovation has also been used in giving and receiving feedback. Focused error feedback, peer evaluation, error logs, student goal setting and post-activity written reflections have been used by researchers to improve the teacher feedback process [19]. Informal, anonymous 'minute evaluations' for example, [20] can be used early in a course and the responses used to provide both students and teachers with rich, rapid 'feed-forward' to improve [21, 22]. This complements post-assessment feedback, which is useful, but often too late to enable constructive responses within limited time-frames.

Critical thinking and creativity are essential. Chan [23] showed that those who are part of an innovative learning group found that critical thinking and creativity were essential in connecting their learning to their field of study, as opposed to the standard groups. Educators need to be creative in designing courses that encourage active learning [24]. However both group work and confidence are essential to help students be expressive and creative. Lastly Chan [24] highlights the need for out-of-the-box thinking approaches to encourage students to learn new skills. Paper, chalk and print, use of projectors, educational toys, television and the basic technologies of writing were once termed teaching innovations. Teachers have extended these traditional teaching methods, using platforms like YouTube for discussions [25] and humor, games and peer teaching to make learning environments lively [26]. Teachers in varied disciplines use artistic work such as writing poems, role play, drawing and creating sculptures [27].

The digital revolution has changed the context of teaching and learning, so why not use its tools to provide the best learning experience for students? Any student in the age group 16-24 years should be an expert in exploiting internet resources. Blogs, podcasts, personal webpages, forums and social networks are increasing student participation and enhancing their participation outside the classrooms. Some projects have identified that allowing students to choose their own technologies has contributed to their progress in learning [28]. Moreover, when students find that learning paradigms seldom use technology, they may feel alienated. Institutions and teachers are responsible for minimizing the digital divide in classrooms. The less the divide, the greater the chances for students to engage with the learning pedagogies.

Few studies have used incentives as a form of innovation to motivate students in learning environment. An incentive based study [29] for performance on mathematical tests reveals that incentives have impacted on students' achievements. A similar study on economics students [30] revealed that their exam performance was boosted when they were provided with grade incentives. Similarly, children's engagement improved in a digital game-based learning experiment [31] on reading when rewards were introduced. Our study focuses on an incentive-driven approach in an interesting environment, a diverse undergraduate Computer Science cohort in a small developing country.

This paper outlines the results of data collected from the students in CS240 – a Software Engineering course during Semester 1, 2015 for the Bachelor of Science or Bachelor of Software Engineering stream. By the end of this course students should be able to understand the basic principles in Software Engineering. The innovative strategies used include Facebook, group learning and group presentations for team work, peer evaluations for assessments and preparation for public speaking. The incentive approach is described in Section 4.

3 METHODOLOGY

This is a work in progress, so the paper documents the 'initiation' stage of a Mixed Methods approach [32] identifying new perspectives and issues that can be complemented by deeper qualitative research which should shed light on the reasons behind student opinions expressed in these data. A Mixed Methods (MM) framework seemed the most appropriate for this work, given the diversity of the cohort and the need to be open to challenging researcher assumptions. Based on these findings, we will need to decide which qualitative methodology best suits this cohort, whether it is Grounded Theory, combined with an ethnographic approach, in which we need to research with students, not just 'on' them [33, 34]. We anticipate including a reflective aspect in student evaluations and/or assessment, which could be analysed using a tool such as N-Vivo.

An incentive driven approach guided and applied innovative methods as well as traditional course work activities (refer to Figure 1). Incentives were used to reward students upon completion of the innovative activities. However, traditional course work activities that were also part of teaching the course are included in the model such as online quiz, assignments and final exam. Students were informed during the first week of the semester about the study and the various activities involved. Participation was voluntary and any student could opt not to take part in activities. All of the students in the class (N = 50) opted to be part of the innovative learning experience and 70% responded to the survey that was posted online towards the end of the course. This high response rate may be due to the lecturer encouraging students to complete it and reinforcing its importance.

Every student was allocated randomly to a group of 6 to 7 members from diverse cultural and social backgrounds and they learned this course as a group in all instances. The terms teams and groups have been used interchangeably in the paper. An online survey consisting of 46 closed ended questions was provided to the respondents after completing the activities. The survey questions were designed to receive feedback from participants about the individual innovative activities and the overall experience about the course. The anonymous online survey was designed using the Moodle platform and distributed online. The responses were downloaded to a spreadsheet and the results were analysed quantitatively to obtain the results and draw graphical illustrations. The results of participants who agreed or strongly agreed to each item in the survey form are considered for analysis.

4 AN INCENTIVE DRIVEN MODEL

Before the activities were introduced, the students in the class were divided into eight groups. Each group had a team leader and teams were asked to choose a creative name. The following emerged: Team Heart soft, Team Code Chefs, Team US BE Engineers, Team Fusion, Team Prime Fusion, Team Software gurus, Team Oceania Software Engineers and Team AKAIANE. Each student participated in the innovative activities as part of a group. During the lectures and tutorials they were assigned to sit with their group and complete their tasks.

Teams were informed of the incentives that they would be entitled to after they completed the various activities. The incentives are listed below:

- Facebook Fancier – The best Facebook post would be chosen and the one who posted it would be awarded as Facebook Fancier. One student would receive a prize for this activity. Section 4 expands on Facebook posting.

- Best Assignments – The teams that did well in each assignment task would be recognized as the best team for each assignment. The course had three assignments and three points were awarded for the team with the best assignment score out of 100. Two points were awarded to the team with the second best score out of 100. One point was awarded to the team that had the third best score. A cumulative sum of the team scores for all the three assignments would determine which team receives the prize for this activity.
- Creative Invention award – Teams were asked to present a creative invention idea and the best idea was awarded at the end of the presentations.
- Academic Excellence – Students who performed well in the traditional coursework activities like the Online Quiz, Assignments and achieved higher overall coursework grade was recognized as the winners of this activity. The total coursework mark for this course was set as 50 and students with a higher score out of 50 will receive prizes in the activity. Top three scores were chosen and awarded first, second and third prizes respectively.
- Best Team – One team was chosen as the best team based on their performance in each of the activities. After every assignment each team would receive a point if they have been the top team for the assignment. Upon completion of the three assignments the team that scored the maximum points would receive a prize for this category. In case of a tie, the lecturer will decide the best team by factoring their scores in Online Quiz.
- Best Team Leader – Team leader of the best team was announced as the best team leader or project manager. The winner received a letter of recommendation from the lecturer for their excellence in project management.
- A special award was also given for a team that attended most of the lectures/tutorials.

5 INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES AND THEIR OUTCOMES

The activities introduced to the teams are outlined below.

5.1 Facebook posts

Students were asked to use a closed group “CS240 Software Engineering,” created for the course in Facebook. Students would post an article (at least three articles for a week) that they had recently read about Information technology advancements and post them with comments. The student who posted the article would also talk about the post for two minutes in the classroom. Other members in the closed group would view, ‘like’ or comment on them.

5.2 PEP Talk

Students were given three minutes in every lecture hour to talk about any topic of interest in computing science. The topic should be in some way relevant to Software Engineering. Each team member took turns to present their ideas, based on a ‘one team, one week policy’.

5.3 Creative IT invention

Each team was given five minutes during Week 13 to present any idea that they thought could be introduced as a new product or concept in the computing science domain. They had to arrive at novel and creative idea that involved an out-of-the-box thinking approach. Teams were given five minutes to present their ideas.

5.4 Group Presentations

Every time a presentation is required for the course - be it the creative idea or the assignment presentation, teams have to present as a group. Other groups would be present and anyone could ask questions about the presentation, including the lecturer, who was present.

5.5 Team work

The participants in the course were divided into eight groups during week 2 and their learning for the course was with their team mates. The learning during lectures and lab sessions or tutorials would occur as team-work and not individually. Assignments in the form of a project were done as team work.

5.6 Wikis

Teams were assigned a separate workspace in the form of wikis in their course page in Moodle. All the deliverables and reference materials produced by each team were deposited in the wikis. Teams collaborate and share documents using the wikis.

5.7 Peer Assessment

Since most of the student tasks were based on group work, there was limited scope to judge the individual contributions of the individuals in a team. Hence, the assignments that were submitted as a team document were assessed for initial grades. The peer assessments of the team members by others in the team, namely the team leader or the deputy team leader, were taken into account before arriving at the final individual grades. A simple marking scheme was used to assess the individual contributions. The criteria gave a mark of 0, 0.25, 0.5 or 1 for each student for a week. After four weeks an average of the score was taken and then multiplied with the assignment marks obtained by the team to arrive at the grades for the individuals in each team.

The outcomes for each category used in analysing the data are discussed below:

5.8 Usefulness of various activities for the Course

Most of the respondents found the innovative activities useful. Team work and group presentations were the most popular activities (Refer to Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Responses for the effects of innovative activities

While the teacher observed general enthusiasm in student participation during Facebook interactions, the activity appeared less popular among the respondents. It may be that given the need to use team building skills in industry, students realise that teamwork preparation is highly relevant. The group presentations were intended

as a supplement to demonstrate their findings in the assignments and to build communication skills. The Pep talks provided good informal preparation for presenting. However the team members were observed to be less interested in the presentations in the class rooms, suggesting a need to prepare them and have trial presentations. Despite this respondents rated them highly.

5.9 Introducing similar activities would enhance learning in other courses

Most courses in this university are taught using a traditional approach, so the question arose, would these participants like such innovative teaching methods in other courses? As shown in Figure 3, many participants would prefer them, with team work, creative invention talks and presentations proving most popular. These students are clearly looking for their teachers to introduce team based activities and creativity based tasks.

Fig. 3. Responses for introducing similar activities in other courses

5.10 Overall assessment factors for the course

Respondents were also asked about their overall assessment of the course based on the factors shown in Figure 4 below. Most agree that the learning was innovative and many believe that the methods used were different and more useful than those in other courses. They also believe that they would improve their learning skills if similar methods were introduced elsewhere. Interestingly, the respondents observe that they benefitted more from the team building skills aspect than the actual course itself. One of the course objectives is to contribute to software production in a team context. Hence, the results in this category show that an innovative approach to team building was well aligned with the course objective and the students found it useful.

Fig. 4. Responses for overall assessment of this course

The following section lists the outcome of the responses for each of the activities in detail.

Fig. 5. Responses for use of some activities in the course

While many students remained active on the Facebook group during the course, not many were actively posting updates on the group page although they were actively checking for updates posted by classmates. The students were required to use the Moodle page as their primary source for course updates and university announcements. Not many students actively participated in the discussions posted on Moodle page but remained active on the Facebook group discussions. The findings raise questions about the data consumption patterns of the students and why they prefer to be active in a Facebook group rather than the Moodle Course page. Further investigation is required to answer these questions and this is beyond the scope of this paper.

Using a PEP talk (introduced earlier in this section) has been useful in helping students to learn about new inventions in the field of computing science. This activity motivated the students to search for new inventions and gain knowledge about them after their class hours. Even those who did not pay close attention in the classroom seem to have been motivated to search for new developments in computing. A similar argument applies to the creative idea talk activity (refer to Figure 5). Studies have emphasized the need for working in groups and their place in software industries [35-37]. Group-based activities have improved student participation in the classes.

Students have benefited from each other when working in groups. Group members who assisted others have improved their mentoring skills, by taking part in the “development of self by the mutual support of equals”[38]. Group presentations helped the students improve their presentation skills, communication and learning capabilities. The presentation aspect of the course needs to be improved by adding a practice presentation with formative feedback. This will reduce the fear of presenting and help students to develop the skill of providing constructive comments to peers. It may also address the next issue.

Not many students were willing to use or learn new software for their presentations during the course. The students seemed willing to actively use tools like Facebook, but the same students’ reluctance to use any new tools for their presentations raises an interesting question: Are the students willing to use only social media tools for learning? What lies behind their reluctance to use new tools? This will be the focus of further study and analysis. Group assignments have helped

students to learn course concepts more easily. Group members assisted each other although some (about 12%) did not contribute equally to the assignment tasks. Non-contributing group members are a common source of friction and this needs further study.

Fig. 6. Responses for Team work

As discussed earlier, students prefer to use tools like Facebook and Dropbox for team collaborations (refer to Figure 6) and are reluctant to use the tools available to them through the course page in Moodle (Wikis). Although students were reluctant to be part of a new team during week 1, they observe that they have been progressively developing their team building skills during the course of this class. This calls for better initial preparation for teamwork in the next course iteration, adapting the Teamwork Foundations strategies which have proved effective elsewhere [21]. These activities focus on supporting and developing intercultural skills as an essential preliminary aspect of learning effectively in groups. They have proved effective with engineering students at all levels in diverse classes in Australia [39]. They address the common initial reluctance of students to move outside their cultural or social friendship groups to form teams.

To conclude, the discussion is summarized below:

- Most of the participants in this diverse Pacific context found the innovative methods in teaching and learning useful.
- Incentives acted as a motivation for participants to engage with innovative teaching methods
- Most of them would prefer to learn in a similar way in other courses.
- An incentive driven model was well suited for this course, as was evident from the student participation and their competitive attitude during the group activities.
- Students are more interested and actively learn when tools and applications that they use in their day-to-day life are introduced in the class rooms, like Facebook, Twitter.
- When students work in teams and deliver tasks in groups their learning is more effective.

- Peer assessments are very useful to evaluate individual performance when tasks are submitted as a group artefact like a group assignment or group presentation.
- More studies need to be carried out to understand why students are reluctant to use online tools that were available for them through the Moodle shell, but prefer to use social networking tools.
- More study needs to be done to understand the outcomes of introducing similar methods in other courses and other disciplines in this developing country context.
- More attention needs to be paid to integrating the intercultural aspect of developing effective teamwork.

6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study and its findings would have been enhanced if more participants had responded to the online survey. Informal in-class minute evaluations at the beginning and end of the semester should provide increased and more detailed responses. If teachers respond to student comments early, students are encouraged to give feedback, as they trust that teachers are listening to them and acting on their suggestions. The innovative methods have proved well suited for a theoretical course like CS240 but it would be interesting to observe if they would suit a practical or more technical course with more laboratory sessions. Further, using the same model for Mathematics and other Engineering courses should also be investigated. Teachers face the challenge of finding time to focus on innovative methods due to the demands of course content as well as peer pressure to concentrate on delivering 'content'. Active learning also challenges students to take responsibility for their learning. Despite the incentives, the teacher found it difficult at times to motivate the students, mainly because this work demands continuous attention and students are pressured to focus on their other courses as well as being comfortable with the simpler traditional assessment methods.

It is unclear if all the participants were active on Facebook, as some of the participants were reluctant to use Facebook posts. The teacher taught another course in semester 2, 2015 which is a follow up course (CS241) to the one used for this study. All the students enrolled for CS241 were part of CS240. It would be worthwhile to compare the effects of the innovative methods in these courses. Generally, students in the region view incentives as some form of reward and are motivated to attend workshops and social events. We introduced incentives in our teaching pedagogy with this idea in mind. However, we were not able to identify if the incentives have motivated students to actively participate in the innovative activities for the course. We will focus our future study on the 'complementarity' aspect of the Mixed Methods framework, in order to identify if there is a correlation between the incentives and their participation in the innovative activities.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Students were more excited and willing to be active participants in lectures and tutorials when incentive driven innovative methods were introduced. Since most of the students are familiar with the latest IT tools, they are well placed to use them for learning. An incentive driven model introduces a healthy competitive approach among students, motivating them to learn more and work together across perceived differences towards achieving a common goal. The activities and the skills they develop are not simply focused on essential course knowledge, which can become rapidly outdated, but prepare them for working in a globalized world. Team work and

completing projects on time are basic skills in any software industry and the participants learn those skills by working together for a common goal. As evident from their responses, most of these participants expressed confidence that they would excel as team leaders in industry after their teamwork experience. This is a work in progress but the inference is that similar innovative approaches can be introduced in other engineering courses and that the students would be willing to participate. The findings also support the need for decision makers in higher education to continue investing in and supporting innovative teaching and learning approaches.

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